

Solvent and structural effects on the photo-reduction of cobalt(III) complexes in aquo-organic solvent media possessing different H-bonding properties

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Abstract : The photo-reduction of a series of cobalt(III) complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{ampy})_2(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ where $\text{ampy} = 2\text{-aminomethylpyridine}$ and $\text{R} = \text{H, Me, Et, } t\text{-Bu, COMe, and CN}$ has been studied in propan-2-ol/water and 1,4-dioxane/water medium. The photo-reduction quantum yield ($\Phi_{\text{Co}^{\text{II}}}$) data were correlated with solvent and structural parameters with an aim to shed some light on the mechanism of these reactions. Increase in the percentage of organic co-solvent in both the medium increased the photo-reduction quantum yield. Correlation of $\Phi_{\text{Co}^{\text{II}}}$ with macroscopic solvent parameters viz. relative permittivity indicated that the reactivity is influenced by both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions. Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic comparison method was used to separate and quantify these effects. H-bonding property of the mixture was found to dominate the solvation and consequently the magnitude of the quantum yield.

Keywords : Cobalt(III) complexes, photo-reduction, solvent effect, Hammett equation.

Introduction

The modeling of solvent effects in coordination chemistry is important and one of the most useful methods to obtain information about mechanism of the reactions¹⁻⁶. During the last few years special attention is being paid towards study of solvent effects on different reactions. A solvent would provide not only the back ground for the reaction to occur but would stabilize the reactants and transition state by solvating them. Particularly, the solute-solvent interaction in binary mixture is more complex than in pure solvents. In binary mixtures, the composition of microsphere can be different. So, the macroscopic properties such as relative permittivity⁷, solvent ionizing power⁸, and/or dipolarity/polarisability⁹ etc., are not sufficient to elucidate the entire solute-solvent interactions on the molecular microscopic level¹⁰. Hence, the effect of solvent on reaction kinetics can be explained by using multi parameter approaches such as Kamlet-Taft equation⁹. Although the separation of solvent effects into various solvent-solvent-solute interaction mechanisms is purely formal, the multi-parameter approach to solvent effects has been shown to work well¹¹.

Structural variation studies are also important for the

study and interpretation of chemical reactions and their mechanisms. These effects were arising from the aromatic types of compound having similar structure with slight deviations such as substituent variation^{12,13}. In continuation of our earlier studies on the effect of solvent and structure on the reactivity of Co^{III} complexes, here in this paper we report these effects on the photo-reduction of a series of Co^{III} complexes of the type, $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{ampy})_2(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ in aqua/organic binary mixtures of varying compositions with an aim to get a better insight into the mechanism of such reactions. These mixtures were chosen because by varying the mole fraction of the constituent solvents, the hydrogen bonding properties of the medium can be varied gradually since propan-2-ol is classified as a typical hydrogen bond donor (HBD) and 1,4-dioxane as a typical non-hydrogen bond donor (non-HBD) solvent¹⁰.

Results and discussion

The solvent and structural effects on the photo-reduction of a series of Co^{III} complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{ampy})_2(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ where $\text{ampy} = 2\text{-aminomethylpyridine}$, $\text{R} = \text{H, Me, Et, } t\text{-Bu, COMe, and CN}$ in vary-

ing concentrations of organic co-solvent (propan-2-ol and 1,4-dioxane) in water was investigated. Attempts have been made to analyze the effect of solvent and structure on the photo-reduction quantum yields ($\Phi_{Co^{II}}$) of these complexes using simple and multiple regression equations. The quantum yields measured at 254 nm for the photo-reduction of all the Co^{III} complexes in various water/propan-2-ol and water/1,4-dioxane binary mixtures are collected in Table 1. It is evident from the results that $\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ increased as the mole fraction of organic co-solvent increased in the mixture. The simplified structures of the reactant and excited state are given below.

The increase in $\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ values with an increase in organic co-solvent in the medium is due to the fact that, the charge transfer transition occurs with an inward flow of electron density that decreases the molecular dipole moment. Consequently, switching to a less polar solvent stabilizes the excited state more than the ground state and thereby increases the quantum yield. A plot of quantum

yield for the photo-reduction of a given Co^{III} complex against the mole fraction of the organic co-solvent in the mixtures are linear ($r > 0.96$) and yielded different slopes in the two binary mixtures (Fig. 1, For R = H, in propan-2-ol/water medium the slope is 7.3 while that in the other mixture is 6.1) indicating difference in the participation of the co-solvent in the solvation of the reactant and/or

Fig. 1. Plot of photo-reduction quantum yield versus mole fraction of organic co-solvents in the mixture.

Table 1. Quantum yields ($10^2\Phi_{Co^{II}}$) for the photo-reduction of $cis-\beta-[Co(ampy)_2(4-R-Py)Cl]Cl_2$ in air-equilibrated solvent mixtures at $25 \pm 1^\circ C$

X^a	Organic co-solvent % (v/v)								
	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
	In water/propan-2-ol media								
H	9.93	10.04	10.13	10.35	10.41	10.50	10.72	10.77	10.90
Me	10.90	10.93	11.02	11.09	11.17	11.21	11.31	11.33	11.65
Et	5.41	6.63	7.05	7.43	7.44	7.57	7.77	7.99	8.14
<i>t</i> -Bu	12.58	13.00	13.59	13.78	13.84	13.93	14.04	14.21	14.57
COMe	12.18	12.31	12.43	12.7	12.75	12.85	12.94	13.12	13.34
CN	12.49	12.74	12.92	13.01	13.09	13.22	13.35	13.54	13.65
	In water/1,4-dioxane media								
H	9.93	10.06	10.13	10.38	10.43	10.47	10.56	10.57	10.76
Me	10.90	11.13	11.25	11.27	11.32	11.38	11.43	11.48	11.67
Et	5.41	5.61	5.69	5.90	6.00	6.11	6.19	6.32	6.51
<i>t</i> -Bu	12.58	12.83	12.93	12.98	13.14	13.26	13.39	13.56	13.68
COMe	12.18	12.38	12.56	12.70	12.81	12.92	12.93	13.00	13.08
CN	12.49	12.61	12.79	12.84	12.91	12.94	12.97	13.05	13.14

^aSubstituent in pyridine moiety.

excited state. Further, this may also be due to the reduction of the metal centre by the solvent (solvent-to-metal charge transfer) to different extent in addition to the reduction by the ligand (LMCT)^{4,14}.

The correlation of photo-reduction quantum yields with inverse of relative permittivity of the medium through Laidler-Eyring⁷ equation is only satisfactory with positive slope ($0.97 \geq r \geq 0.80$ for water/propan-2-ol medium and $0.98 \geq r \geq 0.92$ for water/1,4-dioxane medium). The positive slope indicated that the excited state is less polar than the reactant. Such an excited state will more easily be attained in a medium of lower relative permittivity and hence the increase in quantum yield with an increase in the proportion of organic co-solvent is observed. Similarly, the experimental data also correlates only satisfactorily with donor number ($0.98 \geq r \geq 0.84$ in propan-2-ol/water media and $0.98 \geq r \geq 0.93$ in 1,4-dioxane/water media). The DN^N values employed in the present study were calculated as described earlier¹⁵.

The electrostatic approach to medium effects through macroscopic solvent parameters and neglecting specific solute-solvent interactions often failed in correlating observed solvent effects with physical solvent parameters. In reality, satisfactory quantitative descriptions of medium effects have taken into account all nonspecific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. The separation of solvent polarity into nonspecific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interaction mechanism is purely formal, but, if this separation can be reasonably done, the resultant parameters may be used to interpret solvent effects through such multiple correlations, thus providing information about the type and magnitude of interactions with the solvent^{10,11}.

Thus, the dual dependency of reactivity on solvent composition was tested using Kamlet-Taft equation⁹. The $\log \Phi_{Co^{III}}$ values in different propan-2-ol/water and 1,4-dioxane/water mixtures showed a good correlation via Kamlet-Taft equation with an observed variance of over 90%. This is demonstrated by the observation that, in Figs. 2 and 3, the experimentally determined parameters ($\Phi_{Co^{III}}$) are plotted against the corresponding values estimated using the Kamlet-Taft relationship. As can be seen, this relationship successfully describes the solvent dependence on the Co^{III} to Co^{II} reduction by photochemical

Fig. 2. Experimentally determined quantum yield values for *cis*- β -[Co(ampy)₂(Py)Cl]Cl₂ plotted against the corresponding values estimated using the Kamlet-Taft relationship in water/propan-2-ol media.

Fig. 3. Experimentally determined quantum yield values for *cis*- β -[Co(ampy)₂(Py)Cl]Cl₂ plotted against the corresponding values estimated using the Kamlet-Taft relationship in water/1,4-dioxane media.

path. The statistical results of the correlation and weighted percentage contributions of the solvatochromic parameters are given in Table 2. The results of the multiple correlation analysis indicated that, (i) The specific solute-solvent interactions, as indicated by P_{α} and P_{β} play a

Table 2. Statistical results and weighted percentage contributions for the correlation of photo-reduction quantum yield ($\Phi_{Co^{II}}$) with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters

X^a	$100R^2$	sd	a	b	s	P_α	P_β	P_{π^*}
In water/propan-2-ol media								
H	98	0.002	1.24	1.01	-0.72	39	28	33
Me	95	0.002	-1.78	-1.44	0.02	57	42	1
Et	91	0.020	10.3	-3.29	-10.7	36	10	54
<i>t</i> -Bu	96	0.004	-0.71	-4.42	-2.87	8	45	47
COMe	99	0.002	1.39	1.26	-0.64	40	33	27
CN	98	0.002	0.29	-0.10	-0.70	21	6	73
In water/1,4-dioxane media								
H	93	0.004	-5.06	-57.3	-9.66	7	73	20
Me	90	0.004	0.94	18.0	3.94	4	71	25
Et	97	0.005	-6.01	-84.3	-17.8	6	70	24
<i>t</i> -Bu	98	0.002	16.4	-2.37	-36.9	23	3	74
COMe	91	0.004	18.2	-65.4	-62.8	11	35	54
CN	90	0.003	4.94	-21.7	-18.6	9	38	53

^aSubstituent in pyridine moiety.

major role in governing the reactivity of the complexes.

(ii) In water/propan-2-ol medium the solvent HBD property was found to be dominant as indicated by P_α . The sign of the majority of the coefficients of this term is positive indicating better solvation of the excited state than the reactant¹⁶. Since propan-2-ol is a HBD solvent, increase in its mole fraction in the binary mixture stabilizes the excited state by preferentially solvating it through HBD property and consequently increases the quantum yield. (iii) In the case of water/1,4-dioxane medium the contribution of solvent HBA property was found to be dominant. This is because 1,4-dioxane is a typical HBA solvent and increase in its mole fraction will progressively increase the HBA property of the medium and hence the solvation behavior. The sign of the majority of the coefficient of this term is negative indicating relatively better solvation of the reactant than the excited state through HBA property. Hence, increase in the mole fraction of 1,4-dioxane increases the photo-reduction quantum yield to a relatively lesser extent than in the other solvent mixture. This observation corroborates well with the observed difference in slope values in the plot of quantum yield for the photo-reduction of a given Co^{III} complex against the mole fraction of the organic co-solvent in the mixtures (Fig. 1) as discussed earlier.

It was well established that, a dynamic exchange of solvent molecules exists between the solvation shell of

the excited state and the bulk¹⁶. As the organic co-solvent concentration increases in the mixture, more and more organic solvent molecules are introduced into the solvation shell, thereby increasing the hydrophobic environment of the excited state. Increase in hydrophobicity of the medium stabilizes the excited state (which is less polar than the reactant as indicated by the Laidler-Eyring correlation) through H-bonding interactions and consequently increases the photo-reduction quantum yield as organic co-solvent proportion in the mixture increases.

The effect of structure of the ligand on $\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ was studied by changing the substituent in the pyridine moiety. The $\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ failed to conform to the usual Hammett equation and its modified ones. The plot of $\log \Phi_{Co^{II}}$ versus Hammett's substituent constants, σ is a scatter gram¹⁷. This deviation from Hammett's plot may be due to the fact that the substituents present in the pyridine ligand have no significant effect on the photo-reduction of these complexes as they are far away from the metal centre.

The foregoing results and discussions indicated that the photo-reduction of the cobalt(III) complexes were highly influenced by H-bonding properties of the solvent. The photo-reduction of Co^{III} to Co^{II} in these complexes becomes easier with increase in the percentage of organic co-solvent, propan-2-ol and 1,4-dioxane, in the mixture. The solvent effects on the photo-reduction of these com-

plexes were quantitatively described by the Kamlet-Taft relationship. There is no significant effect on the structural changes in the pyridine ligand.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were of high purity analytical grade (Aldrich, Merck, India). The cobalt(III) complexes, *cis*- β -[Co(ampy)₂(4-R-Py)Cl]Cl₂ where ampy = 2-aminomethylpyridine and R = H, Me, Et, *t*-Bu, COMe, and CN were prepared and purified as described in literature using of ampy ligand¹⁸. The organic co-solvents, propan-2-ol/water and 1,4-dioxane used was spectroscopic grade (Merck, India) and was used as received. Doubly-distilled water was used throughout the work.

Photolysis experiment : Solutions for photolysis contained the Co^{III} complex (4×10^{-3} M), and NaNO₃ (0.1 M). All the solutions prepared contained binary solvents of varying compositions : propan-2-ol/water and 1,4-dioxane/water [0-40% (v/v) of co-solvent]. Steady photolysis experiments were carried out using a low pressure mercury vapour pen-ray quartz lamp (254 nm). Air-equilibrated solutions were used for photolysis and the temperature control was maintained at 25 ± 1 °C. For quantum yield determinations, photolysis was carried out to within less than *ca.* 15% of the total reaction. The incident light intensities were measured by potassium ferrioxalate actinometry¹⁹. Quantum yields were calculated, estimating Co^{II} formed by Kitson's method²⁰. All absorption measurements were carried out using a Shimaduz UV-Vis (UV 240 Graphicord) double beam spectrophotometer.

Linear free energy relationships : The effect of relative permittivity, ϵ , of the medium on reactivity can be described by the following equation of Laidler and Eyring⁷ :

$$d \ln k/d(1/\epsilon_r) = e^2 Z^2 (1/r - 1/r^*)/2kT$$

where k is the rate constant ($\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ in the present case), Z the net charge, r the effective radius and r^* the radius of the activated species.

Since, both specific and nonspecific solute-solvent interactions can influence the reactivity, the data were analyzed using the most celebrated Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic comparison method⁹, which incorporates both the types of interactions within, in the form of the following equation.

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent hydrogen bond donor (HBD) acidity which describes the ability of the solvent to donate a proton, β is the solvent hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) basicity which provides a measure of the solvent's ability to accept a proton (donate an electron pair), in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond, and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ ($\log \Phi_{Co^{II}}$ in the present study) to the indicated solvent parameter.

The effect of substituent on the reactivity was tested using the Hammett equation²¹ :

$$\log k = \log k^0 + \rho\sigma$$

where k is the rate constant ($\Phi_{Co^{II}}$ in the present study), k^0 denotes the statistical quantity corresponding approximately to k for the unsubstituted compound, σ is the substituent constant characteristic of the substituent and ρ is the reaction constant.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regression) and standard deviation (sd)²¹. In case of multiple correlation analysis, the percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed as reported earlier²².

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